

PROBLEMS IN FINANCING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

Maqolada asosan aksiyonerlik jamiyatlarning innovatsion faoliyatini moliyalashtirishdagi muammolar mavjud bo'lib, ularning asosiysi innovatsion kapitalning to'g'ri va aniq baholanishi bilan bog'lik muammolar haqida aytib o'tilgan

KEYWORDS

aksiyodorlik jamiyatlarp innovatsiya
innovatsion kapital innovatsion faoliyat
innovatsion jarayon innovatsion loyihalar

INTRODUCTION

of a modern management system

Efficiency increases

The analysis of the above tables shows that the process of financing innovative activities in joint-stock companies is mainly faced with problems related to the lack of financial resources, high investment risks, and insufficient development of modern financing mechanisms. In particular, the high cost of bank loans and the underdevelopment of the venture capital market limit the possibilities for implementing innovative projects.

The data presented in the table show that for the effective organization of innovative activities, it is important to diversify financing sources, strengthen state support mechanisms, and attract private investment. At the same time, the innovative potential of joint-stock companies can be increased by improving the corporate governance system and developing the venture financing infrastructure..

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